

The Effect of Human Capital on Social Entrepreneurial Orientation among Undergraduate's Students in Malaysia

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Abstract

In an era of entrepreneurship popularity, a growing need exists for scholars and practitioners to develop beyond the mere perceptions or templates regarding the social entrepreneurial orientation among university students and instead have scientific data and scientific results about the impact of human capital on the social entrepreneurial orientation of students. The aim of this research is to study the effect of human capital on social entrepreneurial orientation among undergraduate students in Malaysia. The survey was conducted on 600 students who are social science, and business administration from six universities in Malaysia but only 514 questionnaires were obtained. The study combined exploratory factor analysis with structural equation modeling (SEM) to develop the research model. The findings of this study have theoretical and practical implications for academics and organization practitioners. The results indicated that a direct positive and significant effect of human capital on social entrepreneurial orientation. It was suggested that future research might widen the scope by considering social entrepreneurship-related studies in other categories, such as women, adult or general youth. Also, invite researchers focused on the legal role to support entrepreneurship based on social effect.

Keyword: Human capital, social entrepreneurial orientation

Introduction

Over the last decade, social entrepreneurship has played a crucial role in local advancement among developing countries (Hamid, Hengchao & Mhd-Sarif, 2017; Yiu et al., 2014). Indeed, the application of business solutions to social problems has gradually become a regular practice (Choi & Majumdar, 2014; Cunha & Benneworth, 2014, Sallam et al., 2019), and the use of case studies featuring prominent and innovative profiles of social enterprises and entrepreneurs has recognized social entrepreneurship (Nicolopoulou, 2014). In the case of Malaysia, the development of entrepreneurship as both a practice and a concept has become more vital. The significance of entrepreneurship to the growth of Malaysian economy has been made apparent by the growing number of supportive instruments and policies for entrepreneurs including business advisory services, the creation of a special ministry for entrepreneurs, funding, and physical infrastructures (Ariff & Abubakar, 2003; Nor, 2015).

Undergraduate students are believed to be the most appropriate starting point for receiving intensive training and for being tutored as future innovators and entrepreneurs, and entrepreneurial orientation is an imperative to achieve a lasting innovation orientation among students (Nordin, 2015). Unfortunately, little discussion has occurred, or analysis has been held on the orientation of students toward entrepreneurship in Malaysia and the effects of human capital on social entrepreneurial orientation. This study sought to add to this discussion and fill in a gap in the research.

Few studies have been conducted in the areas of entrepreneurial orientation in Malaysian context (Arham, 2014; Awang et al., 2009, Awang, Ahmad & Subari, 2010; Mohd, 2015). More precisely, academic studies and other scholarly research on how social entrepreneurial orientation of Malaysian students are related to human capital seem to be limited. It is in lieu of this; therefore, this study examined the human capital of

Malaysian students, and further evaluated the nature and effect of these variables on social entrepreneurial orientations.

Problem statement

The Malaysian government is expected to achieve the development of entrepreneurship by the year 2020 to provide the country with a sound framework for sustainable growth as an alternative to the long-term economic development strategy required to achieve its full status as an industrial nation (IRMA, 2017; Patricia, 2012). In achieving this aim, the Malaysian government has recognized the significance of having a knowledgeable productive, and skilled workforce that can contribute to national growth (Awang, Ibrahim & Ayub, 2014). Entrepreneurs are a vital part of this workforce, which essential for raising the productivity level and safeguarding competitive advantage in the current world business environment (Norasmah & Faridah, 2010). Malaysia has placed emphasis on the development and training of university students as important human capital in its effort toward becoming a fully developed nation and a major global player. As a small, open-economy with about 42.3% of its population lies between the ages of 0-24 years (UNICEF, 2014), the need, therefore, to inculcate entrepreneurial skills among the teeming youths is justified.

Accordingly, because entrepreneurial orientation has been demonstrated to be a main determining factor (Ambad & Abdul Wahab, 2016) the deciding factor behind development tendencies (Lumpkin, Brigham & Moss, 2010; Morgan, Anokhin & Wincent, 2016; Păunescu et al., 2013), and social change in any country (Criado-Gomis, Cervera-Taulet & Iniesta-Bonillo, 2017), the Malaysian government has officially acknowledged that several weakness exists in the social entrepreneurial orientation of students, and these deficiencies lead to a lack of entrepreneurship activities among Malaysian youth (Ibrahim & Mahyuddin, 2017). This means that a gap exists between human capital and social entrepreneurial orientation in Malaysia. Several scholarly contributions have indicated that the abilities of graduates in the employment arena are considered very low, with deficiencies and a mismatch of skills between the skills that graduates have and those required by employers and the job market (Economic Planning Unit 2010; Wahid et al., 2011).

Literature Review

Social entrepreneurial orientation

Entrepreneurial orientation has become an increased research domain and attracted the attention of various scholars in recent years, establishing itself among areas in entrepreneurship research and practices (Arbaugh, Cox & Camp, 2009; Wales et al., 2013; Alam et al., 2015; Martens et al., 2016), and as an important construct in entrepreneurial studies (Rauch et al., 2009). Miller (1983) introduced the original framework of entrepreneurial orientation utilizing the dimensions of innovation, proactiveness, and risk-taking to measure entrepreneurship, and many subsequent studies adopted these three dimensions (Cong, Dempsey & Xie, 2017; Covin & Lumpkin, 2011; Covin & Slevin, 1989; Deb & Wiklund, 2017; Rainwater, 2016). This three-dimensional view of entrepreneurial orientation looks at innovativeness (the introduction of new products, processes, and business models), proactiveness (actively entering new spaces with products and seeking leadership positions in the market), and risk-taking (the goodwill of strategic decision-makers to contribute resources to projects with uncertain outcomes). Many studies have summarized these dimensions to create a unique index (Rauch et al., 2009; Smith & Muldrew, 2017; Tang et al., 2008).

The social orientation of entrepreneurs depends on individual characteristics related to personality (Sastre-Castillo, Peris-Ortiz & Valle, 2015). According to Williams and Nadin (2012), social entrepreneurs assign the reasons for their activity into two categories: individualist or social. Individualist reasons embrace the aspiration to work more autonomously, to not have a boss, or to have a new after-retirement occupation. Social

reasons include aiding other people or bettering the environment. Based on the general outlook of research towards social entrepreneurship, Abu-Saifan (2012) found that the research on social entrepreneurship fell short when compared to other fields of entrepreneurship. Abu-Saifan (2012) noted a need for additional studies to explore the different constructs of social entrepreneurship and to increase the general understanding of the topic. The present study seeks to fill this void in an attempt to increase the understanding of how new different variables influence social entrepreneurial orientation. As such, it constitutes an important contribution towards increasing the understanding of social entrepreneurship and how different variables affect social entrepreneurship in different ways.

Human capital

Semantically speaking, the term human capital is simply the combination of words human and capital (Harpan & Draghici, 2014; Kwon, 2009). However, a common understanding of the term has not been so simple, and scholars have debated issues concerning the definition and measurement of human capital for several decades (Veselinova & Parleev, 2017). Different perspectives of human capital have led to different definitions (Florin, Lubatkin & Schulze, 2003; Veselinova & Parleev, 2017). According to Becker (1994), the definition of human capital includes individual knowledge and skills that create commercial value, which comes from general knowledge and skills or from specific individual skills. Others have defined human capital as an investment in the talents, experience, skill, knowledge or other intangible assets of individuals an engine for business growth and the main factor in new business formation (Erbasi, 2016; Kunnas, 2016; Schriver, 2017). However, for many professionals, the term human capital is divisive and inhumane (Mamabolo, Kerrin & Kele, 2017). Martin, McNally, and Kay (2013) investigated the human capital outcomes that students obtained from their study of entrepreneurship. The researchers defined human capital assets like knowledge, skills, and the desire to actually engage in entrepreneurial activities. The researchers conducted a quantitative review of previous studies to examine the human capital assets outcomes of entrepreneurship education for students. Overall, the researchers concluded that entrepreneurship education was positively associated with higher levels of overall human capital assets related to entrepreneurship. Furthermore, they concluded that entrepreneurship education was related to higher levels of knowledge and skills related to entrepreneurship, positive perceptions about entrepreneurship, and actual intentions to engage in entrepreneurial activities (Rainwater, 2016).

The Relationship of Human Capital and Social Entrepreneurial Orientation

A high level of education may be a key factor predicting an entrepreneur's proclivity to explore opportunities that are promising in terms of innovations and knowledge dissemination (Darnihamedani & Hessels, 2016; Soriano, Huarng, 2013; Davidsson & Honig, 2003). Davidsson and Honig (2003) and Grichnik, Brinckmann, Singh & Manigart (2014) showed how budding entrepreneurs with higher levels of human capital enable to use more bootstrapping activities to acquire resources for their intended start-ups. Theoretically speaking, the influence of entrepreneurial learning on the success of start-up companies has had previous research (Beek, 2017), with the literature having often uncovered a positive relationship between education and entrepreneurship (Arenius & Minniti, 2005; Burge, 2017; Delmar & Davidsson, 2000; Rocha, Carneiro & Varum, 2015).

With respect to social entrepreneurship, most research has reported a positive relationship with human capital (Sallam et al., 2019). In reviewing the results of a 2015 GEM survey utilizing interviews of 167,793 adults across the economics of 58 countries, Bosma et al. (2016) demonstrated that the prevalence rate of social

entrepreneurship was higher among educated individuals and that the highest level was among those individuals with post-secondary education. Furthermore, Hoogendoorn, van der Zwan and Thurik's (2011) analysis of 36 high-income countries, and Harding and Cowling's (2006) study of the United Kingdom, and Kachlami's (2014) summary of findings on the issue all demonstrated a positive relationship between education and social entrepreneurship. Bacq and Janssen (2011) study using GEM 2009 survey data on social entrepreneurship for Belgium and the Netherlands shows that social entrepreneurs have higher levels of education than commercial entrepreneurs do. Lastly, Van Ryzin et al. (2009), using the data from an online survey in the US, also confirmed that college-educated individuals were more likely to be social entrepreneurs than non-college education individuals.

Thus, the influence of entrepreneurial learning on the success of start-up companies has been the subject of previous research. In summary, it seems that those individuals with a higher level of education may also have a greater probability of realizing success and fulfilling their personal goals both as entrepreneurs and as employees (Bosma et al., 2016; Gimeno et al., 1997; McDowall & Micinski, 2010).

Research Method

Quantitative research was conducted by distributing questionnaire asking how effect the human capital influencing the youth to social entrepreneurial orientation. This research took both from disciplines of social science and business schools in universities in Malaysia. In this research the responders were students aged between 18 to 26 years in six Universities in Malaysia. The six universities of interest, University of Malaya (UM), University Teknologi Malaysia (UTM), University Putra Malaysia (UPM) University Kebangsaan Malaysia / National University of Malaysia (UKM), University Utara Malaysia (UUM), and University Malaysia Perlis (Unimap) added, the six areas are located in Western Malaysia. The participation in answering the questionnaire is on volunteer basis with no force to answer the questionnaire. A self-administered questionnaire was distributed to the total of 600 respondents to avoid incomplete data, and missing responses from the respondents, 516 (86%) were returned, and 84 (14%) either were out returned or were not completely filled in. The analyses using PLS-SEM With the increasing dissemination of PLS-SEM in social sciences, methodological research has provided various extensions that allow for a more nuanced assessment of data and model relationships.

This questionnaire was adjusted by three lecturers from university Malaysia Perlis to validate the content. The construct validity of the questionnaire is listed in Table 1. The selected research variables meet the conditions proposed by Hair et al. (2013): (1) Composite reliability values reflect the level at which the construct indicators reveal the latent variable, and they should be more than 0.70 ; (2) after varimax rotating, the absolute value of the factor loading must be greater than 0.5; (3) the difference between each of the factor loadings must be greater than 0.3. In other words, the questionnaire used in this study has content validity and construct validity.

A thorough literature review generated a self-administered questionnaire containing four sections. The first part included questions about respondents' demographic characteristics: Gender, Age, Religion, Race, and University. In the second part, respondents provided information on their orient forward social entrepreneurship: Do you have social entrepreneur experience, Are you a member of any non-governmental organization (NGO), Have you ever taken any course or module as follows: entrepreneurial education or entrepreneurial social education. The third part contained seven items used to measure students' orientation to social entrepreneurship. A 5-point Likert scale was used to rate the extent to which respondents agreed or disagreed, ranging from 1 = strongly disagree to 5 = strongly agree. The fourth part which included 15 items

(Table 1), assessed respondents' opinions about human capital that effect students' orientation to social entrepreneurship. Respondents rated the importance of the 15 items on a 5-point Likert scale where 5 was most important, and 1 was least important.

Result

The analysis results of the measurement model show each factor loading value of the measurement models in the scales were all above 0.6, demonstrating the reliability of the scale's indices and dimensions. Composite reliability values were also over 0.7, demonstrating internal consistency. In addition, the values of the scale's average variance extracted (AVE) were all over 0.5, establishing convergent validity (Hair, Hult, Ringle & Sarstedt, 2017) (see Table 1).

Table 1. The result of principal component analysis

Model Construct	Context of measurement items	Loading	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
Social Entrepreneurial Orientation	I see links between seemingly unrelated pieces of information.	0.6902	0.8375	0.5641
	Entrepreneurship is a means of creating jobs and wealth.	0.8205		
	Entrepreneurship serves as an opportunity for one to show ones talent & do what one loves doing.	0.7186		
	Entrepreneurship serves as a link in the process of innovation, development, and economic growth.	0.7683		
Human Capital	Knowledge (information) is required to succeed as a social entrepreneur.	0.7567	0.8606	0.5079
	You need to have a particular skill to be social entrepreneur.	0.6477		
	Working experience makes the social entrepreneur better.	0.7165		
	A social entrepreneur should have leadership traits.(e.g.. recognizing opportunities, working creatively, problem solving, developing new products and services, and putting plan into action).	0.7596		
	Entrepreneurial courses in academic curriculum can made a better social entrepreneur.	0.6935		
	Understanding human capital management is required to better social entrepreneur.	0.6958		

The desired factor loading level for a variable was set at 0.60 (Hair et al., 2006). Of the initial 15 items, 5 were excluded during the scale purification process because they either loaded heavily on more than one factor or did not meet the 0.60-factor loadings cutoff. In the human capital affecting a social entrepreneurial orientation, the factor loadings ranged from 0.699-0.821. All factors had a Cronbach's alpha higher than 0.70 (social entrepreneurial orientation 0.73 and human capital 0.76) which exceeded the acceptance criteria and the 0.7 thresholds recommended by Nunnally (1978) for the test of scale reliability.

In the present study, discriminant validity of the measures was assessed through the Fornell and Larcker's (1981) criterion. Like the correlation matrix shown in Table 2, the diagonal scores are the average variance square root extracted from the latent constructs. Discriminant validity exists if the diagonal elements are greater than other off-diagonal elements shown in the rows and columns. This was the case in the correlation matrix, and hence, discriminant validity was confirmed.

Table 2. Correlations among Constructs and Discriminant Validity

	Human Capital	Social Entrepreneurial Orientation
Human Capital	0.7127	
Social Entrepreneurial Orientation	0.2631	0.751

Demographic profile of the sample: According to Table 3, of the 600 respondents, most respondents were female (66.4%); and males were (33.6%). The greatest number respondents were aged 20 years old and below, which was 48.9% of the total. In term of race, most respondents were Malay, with 391 respondents (74.9%), followed by Chinese, Indian and Others with 80 respondents (15.5%), 31 respondents (6.0%) and 5 respondents (1.0%) respectively, and the Melanau race was the lowest among the respondents with 2 (.4%) of the total sample. In term of religion, Muslims students comprised a majority of the respondents with 398 of the respondents (77.3%) of the total sample, followed by Christianity with 64 of the respondents (12.4%) and Hindu with 31 (6.0%). The smallest with respect to religion was Buddhist, with only 20 of the respondents (3.9%). The table indicated that among the 191 respondents, 37.1% had social entrepreneurial experience, 51.1% had friends or family members who were involved in any social entrepreneurship activities, and only 9.1% were members of a non-governmental organization (NGO). Most respondents (90.7%) did not have a membership in any non-governmental organization (NGO).

Table 3. The Demographic Characteristics of Respondents

Variable	Category	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	173	33.6
	Female	342	66.4
Age	20 years old and below	252	48.9
	21 - 23 years old	228	44.3
	24 - 25 years old	25	4.9
	26 and above	10	1.9
University	UKM	87	16.9
	UUM	91	17.7
	Unimap	50	9.7
	UPM	113	21.9
	UM	135	26.2
	UTM	39	7.6
Race	Malay	391	75.9
	Bidayauh	3	.6
	Chinese	80	15.5
	Iban	3	.6
	Melanau	2	.4

Religion	India	31	6.0
	Other(s)	5	1.0
Religion	Islam	398	77.3
	Christianity	64	12.4
	Buddhist	20	3.9
	Hindu	31	6.0
	Other(s)	2	.4
	Do you have a social entrepreneur experience?	Yes	191
	No	324	62.9
Are you a member of any nongovernmental organization (NGO)?	Yes	47	9.1
	No	467	90.7
Do you have any friends/families involved in any social entrepreneurship activities?	Yes	263	51.1
	No	250	48.5

Multiple regression analysis results: After factor analysis provided factors that respondents viewed as affecting their orientation to social entrepreneurship, Multiple Linear Regression (MLR) using a standard regression method was conducted to identify factors that can predict the orientation to social entrepreneurship according to their level of importance. Table 4 presents the collinearity statistics for independent variable (human capital) present in the model used in this study. The correlations between the variables were less than 0.90, showing that no issue related to multicollinearity existed. The tolerance values were 0.603, and VIF values were 1.454. Therefore, the findings indicated that no violations of the assumption of multicollinearity were present.

Table 4. Tests for Multicollinearity

Model		Collinearity Statistics	
		Tolerance	VIF Value
Human capital	Social entrepreneurship orientation	.688	1.454

The results of the Multiple Linear Regression (MLR) analysis. Based on these results, the overall MLR model with the predictor of human capital to explain the variation in social entrepreneurial orientation ($F_2 = 0.398$, $df = 50$; $p = 0.000$). The predictability of the human capital variable in the following: Human capital and social

entrepreneurial orientation were highly significant ($\beta = 0.1302$, $t = 5.2292$, $P = 0.000$), and, hence, the hypothesis was supported of this study.

Discussion

The finding that human capital influences social entrepreneurial orientation is consistent with Zain Akram & Ghani (2010), who found that human capital had a strong effect on social entrepreneurial orientation. Generally, the findings of this current provide proof to support the earlier studies (Arenius & Minniti, 2005; Burge, 2017; Davidsson & Honig, 2003; Jiménez et al., 2015; Rocha et al., 2015). According to Iyigun and Owen (1998), Rosenbusch et al. (2009), Unger et al. (2011) and Urban and Kongo (2015) all found that human capital positively affects entrepreneurship. Specifically, the findings of the current study are consistent the results drawn from the GEM survey that rate of social entrepreneurship was higher among all educated individuals and was the highest for individuals with post-secondary education. This means that key predictor of social entrepreneurial orientation is the educational context of a community (Bosma et al., 2016).

The next significant finding was related to the hypotheses of this study, which posited a significant relationship between human capital and social entrepreneurial orientation among universities students. This means that youth will be oriented to social entrepreneurship if the human capital (knowledge, skills, and personality attributes) are high. Conversely, hand, youth will not be oriented to social entrepreneurship if human capital is weak.

Similar to the findings of many past studies, the findings of the current study also provided strong empirical support for this relationship. The findings determined a positive and significant effect of human capital in helping youth to grow and to succeed in social entrepreneurship. This means that, when their enhanced knowledge and skills help them to grow and succeed, then these college graduates are more likely to increase their own productivity and the productivity of their co-workers and employers, and the productivity of physical capital.

This current study expands the understanding of the nature of human capital, as well as its influence on the social entrepreneurial orientation of youth. The achievements of NGOs rests upon their ability to innovate and create new products (e.g., Wang & Ke, 2016; Zahra & Covin, 1995). Therefore, understanding the roots of social entrepreneurial activity is important. Furthermore, a gap exists in the understanding of social entrepreneurial orientation when it comes to the resources needed to support these activities. Specifically, although conceptual arguments have been made for the importance of intangible, and knowledge-based resources as human capital (e.g., Floyd & Wooldridge, 1999), there has been little in the way of empirical studies. This current study fills this gap in the literature. In addition, the results are important for promoting social entrepreneurial organizations. That is because promoting social entrepreneurship can reduce the costs and increase the quality of public services and goods delivery in the country (Hassan et al., 2018).

Implications of the Findings and Future Directions

Engaging in social entrepreneurship education will stimulate research and present opportunities to engage in social entrepreneurship that will enhance education, business, and society conjointly (Santos, 2012). According to James and Schmitz (2011), a “curricular shift is required in response to the demand to redress unsustainable business practices and to redefine the role of business in society” (p. 334). Social entrepreneurial research and education can provide business students with the necessary knowledge and skills, theory, and practices needed to operate a triple bottom line, which is one that realigns the role of business in society.

The findings of this study could be utilized to identify a potential need for social entrepreneurship academic programs or degrees within the business school. Currently, academic programs exist at Malaysian universities, within academia, along with institutions designed to educate and further the mission of the social entrepreneur. Within the business sector and academia, a lack of a clear social entrepreneur theory exists (Tishler, 2019). The

absence of a clear theory is coupled with a lack of social entrepreneurship courses and programs offered by many business schools in Malaysia.

Finally, this study has made additions to the empirical knowledge of social entrepreneurial orientation for an important and a large group of society in Malaysia and provides an important first step in understanding the role human capital that could influence the social entrepreneurial orientation in Malaysia. Many opportunities are available for future investigation into social entrepreneurship practices and social values in a community.

Conclusion

Although this study focused on the social entrepreneurial orientation among students, future research may widen the scope by considering social entrepreneurship-related studies in other categories, such as women, adult or general youth. Also, invite researchers focused on the legal role to support entrepreneurship based on social effect. The results demonstrate that human capital has a significant effect on social entrepreneurial orientation and human capital serve as intangible resources and capabilities that can benefit develop the social entrepreneurship among youth, and thereby improve performance of economic value. Grounded on the results of this study, other researchers can continue to expand investigations about whether human capital is positively related to the social entrepreneurial orientations of students, or whether human capital has no real-world impacts on the social entrepreneurial orientations of students.

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